

Teachers' Awareness and Legal Implications of their Conducts on Students' Discipline in Secondary Schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study examined teachers' awareness about the legal implications of their conduct on students' discipline in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research objectives, questions and research hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study, and a population of 1080 secondary school teachers was studied. A total sample size of 292 teachers was selected using a simple random sampling technique. A researcher-developed instrument tagged "Teachers Awareness and Legal Implications of the Conduct and Students Discipline Questionnaire (TALICSDQ)" was used for data collection. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was tested using the Cronbach alpha, which yielded 0.79. The mean statistical tool was used to answer the research questions, and an independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that the extent of awareness and sensitisation about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline is great. Also, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and sensitisation about the legal implication of their conduct on students' discipline in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State. It was recommended that the Ministry of Education should organise workshops and training programmes for teachers on student discipline management and legal implications.

Keywords:

Teachers, Awareness, Legal implication and Conducts, Students

Introduction

One of the most neglected aspects of educational administration is creating awareness among teachers and acquainting them with the legal implications of their conduct in secondary schools. Teacher awareness and teacher-student relationships are crucial in secondary schools, and discipline plays a vital role in maintaining a conducive learning environment. However, teachers' actions can have legal consequences, and awareness of these implications is essential to avoid legal issues and ensure a safe and supportive environment for students. For effective learning and teaching, there must be a harmonious and stable school environment. This can only be achieved when there is appropriate maintenance of the school's rules and regulations. School administrators play a crucial role in providing operational blueprints for discipline, training teachers on disciplinary methods and their implications, ensuring consistent enforcement of school rules and regulations, and promoting a culture of respect and responsibility. Learning can only thrive in a disciplined environment. Hence, the task of student discipline can be carried out in various ways. According to Obobong (2021), teaching also includes processes of child discipline. He enumerates disciplinary methods to include upstanding, exclusive repetition, elective reward, praise denial, public rebuke, counsellor attention, warning letters, grass cutting, fatigue, and outright expulsion when necessary. Notably, there is no recommendation for flogging erring students in his work. However, experience, observation, and findings show that most secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State uphold caning or flogging of erring students as a highly regarded practice. Udofot (2020) reported findings on the widespread use of sticks for discipline in secondary schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, and highlighted the legal implications. He further lamented the inadequate awareness among teachers and parents, attributing this to the colonial teaching and learning methods that many parents and teachers experienced. In all cases, the task of providing the necessary operational blueprint falls on the school administrators, who are expected to educate their staff on the methods, measures, and implications of school discipline.

Teacher indiscipline refers to the failure to adhere to the expected standards of behaviour by teachers. In line with this, Kaponda (2021) defined teacher indiscipline as acts of behaviour by teachers that compromise teaching and learning in schools. According to other scholars, discipline in secondary schools is essential as it enhances the process of maintaining order and stability (Obobong, 2021), encourages responsible behaviour (Kaponda, 2021), improves academic performance (Hattie, 2015), and fosters positive relationships between teachers and students (Wubbels, 2011).

In secondary schools, common models that influence discipline include the Traditional Model, also known as the Individual Fulfillment Approach, which focuses on authority, obedience, punishment, and compliance with rules and regulations. The Progressive Model, also called Scholarly Discipline, emphasises a student-centred approach, encouraging self-regulation, personal responsibility, and

critical thinking. The Humanistic Model, or Educational Technology Model, focuses on repairing harm, promoting accountability, and prioritising student well-being, dignity, and self-actualisation while fostering a positive school climate, empathy, and mutual respect. Finally, the Restorative Justice Model, also referred to as the Social Construction and Community-Building Approach, emphasises repairing harm and building a sense of community to foster social responsibility.

Statement of the problem

Despite the critical role teachers play in maintaining a safe and supportive learning environment, many of them are unaware of the legal implications of their conduct in student discipline. This knowledge gap can lead to unintentional violations of students' rights, inconsistent application of discipline policies, failure to address bullying and harassment, inadequate reporting of misconduct, legal liability for teachers and schools, and negative impacts on student well-being and academic achievement.

State secondary schools in Nigeria are established and governed by education laws, which are legally certified by government authorities to monitor personnel and student activities. School principals are expected to understand, observe, and enforce these laws to ensure effective school administration. As administrators, principals are responsible for keeping their schools legally compliant. Teachers, in turn, must be knowledgeable about education law to apply relevant legal principles in their school communities.

It is essential to assess whether teachers are adequately informed about the laws that govern their profession, including those related to teachers' misconduct, torts, the Child Rights Act, and disciplinary actions. A lack of knowledge can result in decisions that infringe on students' rights. This study seeks to address the problem by examining teachers' awareness of the legal implications of their conduct on student discipline in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area, thereby bridging gaps in location and content.

Purpose of the study

The study essentially seeks to:

- i. examine the extent of awareness about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline in the public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area;
- ii. examine the extent of sensitisation about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline in the public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Research Questions

i. What is the extent of awareness on the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline in the public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

ii. What is the extent of sensitisation on the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline in the public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

i. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and legal implications of their conduct on students' discipline in secondary school in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

ii. There is no significant difference between the mean score of experienced teachers and less experienced teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and legal implications of their conduct on students' discipline in secondary school in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State

Literature Review

For a total comprehension, this section is presented in subheadings thus:

Teachers' Awareness of Legal Implications

Teachers' awareness of the legal implications of their actions is critical for maintaining a safe and supportive school environment. According to Barton (2017), inadequate awareness can lead to legal issues such as violations of students' rights, inconsistent enforcement of disciplinary policies, and negative impacts on student well-being and academic performance. Teachers who understand education laws and policies are more likely to foster an environment that supports students' rights and prevents potential legal challenges (UNESCO, 2020).

In corroboration to the above, Udofot (2020) explored the influence of colonial teaching practices on discipline in Nigerian schools and highlighted the widespread use of corporal punishment, despite its potential legal consequences. He emphasised the importance of teacher awareness of the Child Rights Act and other relevant laws to prevent the continuation of harmful disciplinary practices. Similarly, the National Human Rights Commission (2019) underscored the need for teacher training on students' rights and discipline management.

Teacher-Student Relationships and Discipline

The quality of teacher-student relationships plays a significant role in maintaining discipline. Wubbels (2011), in his research titled *Teacher-student relationships and academic achievement*, highlighted the importance of positive teacher-student relationships in fostering a conducive learning environment. Teachers who are aware of the legal and ethical boundaries in their relationships with students are better equipped to handle disciplinary situations fairly and respectfully. This awareness is essential for promoting trust and mutual respect, which are crucial for student engagement and achievement.

Obobong (2021) outlined various disciplinary methods that can be applied in schools, including public rebukes, counselling sessions, and warnings, while emphasising the importance of avoiding corporal punishment. The study suggested that school administrators should provide operational blueprints and ensure teachers are adequately trained in managing student behaviour without violating students' rights.

Disciplinary Models in Education

Several models guide disciplinary practices in schools. The Traditional Model emphasises authority, obedience, and punishment, while the Progressive Model focusses on student-centred approaches and self-regulation (Gershon, 2017). The humanistic model prioritises student well-being and aims to repair harm and foster empathy. Lastly, the Restorative Justice Model emphasises community-building and repairing relationships as a way to address student misconduct (Kaponda, 2021). Each model requires teachers to be aware of their legal responsibilities to ensure the appropriate application of disciplinary measures without infringing on students' rights.

Need for Sensitisation and Training

Sensitisation and training programmes are essential for enhancing teachers' awareness of the legal implications of their conduct. Hattie (2015) argued that continuous professional development is critical for ensuring that teachers are equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary for managing student discipline effectively. Workshops and training sessions organised by educational authorities can help bridge knowledge gaps and ensure teachers remain compliant with legal requirements.

The gap in this literature review lies in its limited use of context-specific studies from Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, minimal exploration of demographic factors, insufficient discussion of training programmes and legal frameworks, and lack of focus on recent legal reforms impacting teachers' awareness of student discipline in the region. Hence this research aims to explore this gap by examining the extent of teachers' awareness and sensitisation regarding the legal implications of their conduct on student discipline in secondary schools in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the study addresses the lack of local context-specific studies, investigates potential differences in awareness based on gender and experience, and highlights the need for improved training programmes and understanding of legal frameworks governing student discipline in the region.

Theoretical Review

Social Contract Theory

This theory was founded by Thomas Hobbes (1651) and John Locke (1689). Its postulation is that individuals agree to surrender some personal freedoms in exchange for the protection and stability provided by a governing authority. In applying this to teachers, it highlights the importance of awareness regarding the legal implications of student discipline. Teachers are expected to operate within the framework established by the school authority in compliance with the law, regardless of their personal beliefs or values.

Teachers have the following responsibilities under this framework:

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- **Duty to Maintain Order:** Teachers, as authority figures, have a responsibility to maintain a safe and orderly learning environment, balancing individual rights with the greater good.
- **Respect Student Rights:** Teachers must respect students' rights and freedoms, ensuring fair treatment and due process in disciplinary actions.
- **Operate Within Professional Boundaries:** Teachers must establish and maintain professional boundaries, avoiding actions that could be perceived as arbitrary, biased, or harmful.
- **Bear Consequences for Misconduct:** Teachers who violate their contractual obligations or engage in misconduct may face legal and professional consequences.
- **Awareness of Power Dynamics:** Teachers should recognise the power imbalance in teacher-student relationships and exercise their authority judiciously, avoiding any abuse of power.
- **Compliance with Policies and Procedures:** Teachers must be aware of and follow school policies and procedures, ensuring consistency and fairness in disciplinary actions.
- **Obligation to Report Misconduct:** Teachers have a duty to report any misconduct by colleagues to promote a culture of accountability and respect for students' rights.

By understanding Social Contract Theory, teachers can better appreciate their role in maintaining a safe and supportive learning environment, upholding students' rights, and exercising their authority responsibly to avoid legal liability. Moreover, Gershon (2017) highlighted the four disciplinary models commonly applied in schooling approaches.

Methodology

Design of the Study

The design of the study is descriptive survey design.

Area of the Study

The area of the study is Uyo Local Government Area, the capital of Akwa Ibom State. Akwa Ibom State is predominantly a civil service area. It has a mixed population of people from neighbouring states who come to do business. Along with English, the main spoken language is Ibibio language. To a large extent, most small-scale business owners in this area have a reasonable level of educational qualification. The study area needs adequate security in the school in order to guarantee the safety of students while in school. Hence, the study sought to examine the extent of awareness of the legal implications of teachers conduct on students discipline in the public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Population of the Study

The population of the study was 1080 secondary school teachers in all the 14 public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area in the 2024/2025 academic session (Akwa Ibom state Ministry of Education).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A total number of 292 teachers were selected using a simple random sampling technique. Twenty (21) teachers were selected from 12 schools while 10 teachers were selected from 2 secondary schools in the study area.

Instrumentation

The instrument used for the study was a questionnaire developed by the researcher tagged Teachers Awareness and Legal Implications of their Conduct and Students Discipline Questionnaire (TALICSDQ). The items in the questionnaire were derived from the research objectives and the research questions. The first section presents the respondents demographic background, while the second section deals with teachers' opinions on awareness and sensitisation on the legal implications of their conduct on students' discipline. The items were measured by a four-point type scale ranging from Very Great Extent (VGE) – 4, Great Extent (GE) – 3, Little Extent (LE) – 2 to Very Little Extent (VLE) – 1.

Validation of Instrument

Expert judgement was required to ascertain the validity of the items in the questionnaire. Two experts in the field of education, who are professors, validated all the items in the questionnaire. The wording of the items was also checked for clarity. One item in the questionnaire was deleted for irrelevance while three ambiguously worded items were restructured to reflect clarity. After the corrections, the two experts found the items to be suitable for administration.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability co-efficient of the instrument was tested by using the Cronbach alpha which yielded a reliability co-efficient of 0.79.

Data Collection Technique

The instrument was administered by the researcher with the two trained research assistants. All the 292 copies of the questionnaire administered were collected for analysis.

Data Analysis Technique

Mean statistical tool was used to answer the research questions and independent t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Decision Rule

A mean score of 2.50 and above was used to indicate that there is a significant difference to a great extent, while a mean score below 2.50 indicated a difference to a little extent.

The null hypotheses were rejected when the p-value was less than or equal to the .05 level of significance. Conversely, the null hypotheses were accepted when the p-value was greater than the .05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of awareness regarding the legal implications of teachers' conduct on student discipline in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area?

Table 1: Summary of Mean responses on the extent of awareness about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline

SN	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Acquiring the necessary skills in relating with students in the school	3.30	0.88	GE
2	Receiving continuous re-training on the legal implications of teachers conduct for effective delivery	3.20	0.86	GE
3	Acquiring knowledge of education law helps me know my bounds of operation as a teacher.	2.90	0.89	GE
4	Being aware of the legal implication of teachers conduct make me know how to discipline students	3.40	0.82	GE
Grand Mean		3.20		GE

Table 1 shows the summary of the mean score for items 1 – 4. The Grand Mean of 3.20 means that the extent of awareness about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline is great. The standard deviation ranges from 0.82 to 0.89, meaning that respondents' opinions were not divergent from each other.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of sensitisation about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline in the public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Table 2: Summary of Mean responses on the extent of sensitization about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline

SN	Items	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Being sensitised makes me suppress the repeat of negative behaviour in the student on which punishment was administered	3.34	0.98	GE
2	Being sensitized makes me to avoid considering punishment as the only disciplinary measures to be used on wrong doers.	3.22	0.81	GE
3	Being sensitized makes to avoid using punishment as the means of reform	3.16	0.87	GE
4	Being sensitized makes to prevent students from damaging school properties	3.54	0.92	GE
Grand Mean		3.32		GE

Table 2 shows the summary of the mean score for items 1 – 4. The Grand Mean of 3.32 means that the extent of sensitisation about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline is great. The standard deviation ranges from 0.87 to 0.98, meaning that respondents' opinions were not divergent from each other.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness about the legal implication of their conduct and student's discipline in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State

Table 3: Independent t-test analysis regarding the difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent teacher's awareness about the legal implications of teachers conduct on students' discipline in the public secondary schools n= 292

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Sig.	Remarks
Male	130	3.71	0.76	3.42	0.001	Significant
Female	162	3.60	0.93			

*significant at .05 alpha level; df=290

The result in Table 4.4 showed that the computed t-value is 3.42, while its corresponding probability level of significance is 0.001. This level of significance is less than .05; hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and legal implication of their conduct in secondary school in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean score of experienced teachers less experienced teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and legal implication of their conduct in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State

Table 4: Independent t-test analysis on the difference between the mean score of experience teachers less experience teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and legal implication of their conduct in secondary school n = 292

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Sig.	Remarks
Male	130	3.39	0.79	6.30	0.003	Significant
Female	162	3.39	0.84			

*significant at .05 alpha level; df = 290

The result in Table 4 showed that the computed t-value is 6.30, while its corresponding probability level of significance is 0.003. This level of significance is less than .05; hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between the mean score of experienced teachers and less experienced teachers on the extent of teachers' awareness and legal implications of their conduct in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that the extent of awareness regarding the legal implications of teachers' conduct on student discipline is significant. Additionally, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on their awareness of these legal implications in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Since teachers' actions can have legal consequences, awareness of these implications is crucial to avoid legal issues and to ensure a safe and supportive environment for students.

For effective teaching and learning, a harmonious and stable school environment is essential. The responsibility of providing the necessary operational framework rests with the school administrators, who are expected to educate their staff on the methods, measures, and implications of school discipline.

Again, the extent of sensitisation about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline is great. Also, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the extent of teachers' sensitisation about the legal implication of their conduct and students' discipline in secondary school in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State. Discipline to include upstanding, exclusive repetition, elective reward, praise denial, public rebuke, counsellors' attention, appearing/warning letter, and grass cutting when necessary. Worth of note is that there is no recommendation for flogging of erring students here. But experience, observation and findings show that most secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State uphold caning or flogging of erring students in high esteem.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the extent of awareness regarding the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline is significant. It was observed that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers concerning their awareness of these legal

implications in secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The study also revealed that the extent of sensitisation about the legal implications of teachers' conduct on students' discipline is substantial, with no significant difference between male and female teachers' mean scores on this measure. Therefore, there is a need for increased awareness and sensitisation to ensure teachers are adequately equipped to manage students' discipline while remaining aware of the legal consequences of their actions.

Recommendations

From the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Ministry of Education should organise workshops and training programmes for teachers on student discipline management and legal implications.
2. The State Secondary Education Board should develop and communicate clear school policies and guidelines on student discipline to teachers.
3. The government should provide resources and support for teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in managing students' behaviour.
4. The State Secondary Education Board should provide teachers with training on child rights and discipline.
6. The Ministry of Education should encourage the students to report abuse by teachers and others.

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TEACHERS AWARENESS AND LEGAL IMPLICATIONS OF THEIR CONDUCTS AND STUDENTS DISCIPLINE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS QUESTIONNAIRE (TALICSDQ)

Instruction: Tick in the box that reflects your answer

Gender: Male []

Female []

Very Great Extent (VGE) – 4

Little Extent (LE) – 2

(VLE) – 1.

Great Extent (GE) – 3

Very Little Extent

.ISN	ITEMS	VGE	GE	LE	VLE
	AWARENESS				
1	Acquiring the necessary skills in relating with students in the school				
2	Receiving continuous re-training on the legal implications of teachers conduct for effective delivery				
3	Acquiring knowledge of education law helps me know my bounds of operation as a teacher.				
4	Being aware of the legal implication of teachers conduct make me know how to discipline students				
	SENSITISATION				
5	Being sensitized makes me suppress the repeat of negative behavior in the student on which punishment was administered				
6	Being sensitized makes me to avoid considering punishment as the only disciplinary measures to be used on wrong doers.				
7	Being sensitized makes to avoid using punishment as the means of reform				
8	Being sensitized makes to prevent students from damaging school properties				